

THE EFFECT OF PUBLIC DEBT ON POVERTY REDUCTION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The broad objective of this study was to analyze the effect of public debt on poverty reduction in Nigeria for the period 1981-2020. The study adopts ex-post facto research design. Multiple regression analysis was utilized in the study in which the Ordinary least square regression method was used in the analysis. Data obtained from the 2021 Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin, and WDI on poverty reduction (POVR), external debt (EXD), domestic debt (DDs), total public debt service (PDS), primary school enrollment rate (PSENr) and government expenditure on social service (SOCEXP) were analyzed in the study. The results from the OLS regression analysis revealed that external debt has a negative and significant impact on poverty reduction while domestic debt has a positive and insignificant effect on poverty reduction. The results also showed that public debt service (PDS) has a negative and insignificant effect on poverty reduction in Nigeria. Thus, this study recommends that External debts should be discouraged: the national assembly should discourage the executive arm of Nigerian government from engaging into subsequent external borrowing and ensures that the institutions of government saddled with debt and finance management (the debt management office and ministry of finance) are strengthen; and that laws that would checkmate misappropriation of public funds are made.

Keywords: Public Debt, External Debt, Domestic Debt, and Poverty Reduction.

1 Introduction

Governments of nations across the world require monetary resources to carryout programmes that would better the socio-economic fortunes of the citizenry within their national boundaries. Most times, nations are faced with insufficient funds to undertake handsome programmes expected to propel economic growth and

development and by implication improve the wellbeing and standard of living of the populace. Thus, government of such nations usually takes the option of mobilizing funds (in the form loans or debt) from within and outside the economy to cushion the effect of the insufficient funds. Consequently, Sulaiman and Azeez (2012) argue that no government is an island on its own and would require aid so as to perform efficiently and effectively. Furthermore, Okwu, Obiwuru, Obiakor, and Oluwalaiye (2016) claim that economic research shows that moderate levels of borrowing have the ability to stimulate growth in a developing country's economy. According to Mbah, Umunna, and Agu (2016), governments require a significant amount of capital finance through investment expenditures on infrastructural and productive capacity development to achieve the ultimate goal of sustainable economic growth; thus, due to a lack of adequate capital due to low savings, most developing countries resort to borrowing from external sources to bridge the gap.

The necessity for a nation's government to take on debt is usually dictated by the disparity between generated revenue and present critical investment demands, which, if not met, might exacerbate the economic situation of its citizens. The necessity to re-finance maturing debt commitments may also necessitate debt (Ogbeifin, 2007 cited in Adejuwon, James and Soneye, 2010).

In reality, most less developed economies such as Nigeria are usually faced with deficit budgetary system occasioned by poor revenue generation machineries; as such, government borrowing becomes a more realistic and apparent option. Expectedly, the debt inclination of such nations should be pinned down to specific infrastructural development activities undertaken with the proceeds of the loans, such that the economic benefits that accrue from there result to significant boost in the economic status of the nation. Thus, the availability of fund (through the loan) enables the economy of the today's debtor nation to become a tomorrow's economically balance nation with the resultant ability to easily offset the debt and remain better disposed to deliver quality economic service to the citizenry. Here lies the main essence of public debt. To this aim, the quantity of capital investment and general economic development programs conducted with borrowed money justifies a country's public debt. However, it is puzzling to note that Nigeria's debt history does not appear to be consistent with this ideal definition of governmental borrowing.

A review of the loan inclination of Nigeria against the backdrop of her infrastructural and human development and the general standard of living of the Nigerian people (as evidenced by the nation's poverty rate, unemployment rate, dilapidated roads, ailing healthcare, epileptic power supply, poor educational system, low human development index, among others) leave great worry as to what really has the

government achieved with the huge debt inclination over the years. For instance, between 1995 to 2004, Nigeria's external debt burden increased from N716.87 billion to N4,890.27 billion representing an increase of approximately 682%; on the other hand, the nation's domestic debt figures stood for N477.73 billion (1995) and N1,370.33 billion (2004); representing an increase of 287%. The nation's unemployment rate was 1.9% in 1995 and 13.4% in 2004. The question remains; how much has these tremendous increases in the loan proceeds to the coffers of Nigeria's government translated to improved economic disposition of Nigerian nation and her people.

In addition, by 2005, Nigeria had made a request to her creditors for debt forgiveness, promising to reinvest the funds required to service the loans in infrastructure development if her creditors agreed to erase her massive debt burden. The agitation was successful in that the nation's loan to the Paris and London Clubs, which stood at N4,196.84 billion and N196.16 billion respectively in 2004, was completely forgiven in 2005, so that the two clubs' loan balance was zero in 2006, bringing Nigeria's total external loan disposition from N4,890.27 billion in 2004 to N451.46 billion in 2006 (CBN, 2018). It is indeed worrisome that after the debt pardoning of 2005, the debt profile of the country has gradually risen again; external debt figures have risen from N451.46 billion in 2006 to N15.855 trillion in 2021 while the domestic debt profile galloped from N1,753.26 billion to N19,242 trillion within the same period (CBN, 2021). Altogether, the total debt profile of the federal government of Nigeria rose from N2,204.72 billion in 2006 to N35.097 trillion in 2021; yet, critical sectors of the economy such as education, electricity, transport and health, etc. show no clear evidence of commensurate improvement. One wonders therefore how the money saved from servicing the debt since the loan pardon of 2005 and the additional loans taken by the government of Nigeria since then have influenced the nation's economic performance and wellbeing of its citizenry.

According to Ekpo and Udo (2013), social unrest and poverty has witnessed a phenomenal increase beginning from the 1980s when public debt burden began to assume monstrous posture. In recent times, the rates of insecurity, bombing, and terrorists' activities in Nigeria have raised serious concerns with the country being described in some quarters as a failed state. Social infrastructure is in a deplorable condition and capacity utilization in manufacturing and other productive sectors with huge employment potential have remained low. Consequently, the rate of poverty in the country has increased tremendously. Sometime the country is referred to as the poverty capital of the world. Thus, given the present deteriorating economic and social conditions in the country at present, it is doubtful whether the procurement of public debt has any positive significant effect on poverty reduction and economic growth in Nigeria.

Can it be affirmed that the huge debt inclination of Nigeria is justifiable by the present status of the nation's economic development indices; how has this high debt profile reflected on the nation's social and economic performance? These form the basis for this study; hence, this study is developed to establish empirically the justification or otherwise of the high debt disposition of Nigeria on her socioeconomic performance. The main objective of this study is to investigate the effect of public debt on poverty reduction in Nigeria.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Framework

2.1.1 The Debt Overhang Theory

The debt overhang theory predicts a negative relationship between the public debt and economic development which are the two key variables of this study. Proponents of this theory believe that as external debt rises above a country's repayment ability, investment is discouraged by the expectation of higher future taxes; thus, the uncertainty associated with high debt, low probability of debt relief and high chances of default (in that regard) reduces investors' incentives and economic growth; as a consequence, high debt service may crowd out private investment (Sachs, 1989; Cohen, 1993); thus, leading to poor economic performance of a country.

The debt overhang theory, according to Arit (2013) holds that debt affects the economic growth through the disincentive effect and illiquidity effect. The debt stock (volume of debt) is concerned with if the country has the assets required to clear this debt in the long run which affects the economic growth through the disincentive aspect of the debt overhang. The debt service burden (flow of debt payments) is a short-term problem concerned with how the debt payments can be serviced from the current income and this affects the economic growth through the illiquidity aspect of the debt overhang which thus results to crowding out effect. In fact, the disincentive effect discourages future investments as investment (capital project) spending of the government will reduce, private investment (foreign direct investment) will be discouraged, leading to a slowdown in economic performance. The cycle continues with further reduction in investment following the economic slowdown, an increase in the debt income ratio, and a reinforcement of the disincentive effect, which ultimately leads to stagnation.

In the face of the foregoing, the debtor country is plunged into liquidity trap (a state of illiquidity) as the indebted country mobilizes every available resource to service debt rather than invest in its economy; thus, debt burden crowds out public capital investment in the economy (crowding out effect). Evidently, the key drive for this study is premised on the nature of debt inclination of Nigeria which could better be

described as unbearable against the backdrop of the nation's continued poor economic development status with respect to infrastructural development (public capital investment) and human development. At the end of the day, this inevitably leads to the nation's incapacity to return the debts it has taken out due to the scarcity of "economic-development-driven investments" that would provide the required economic dividend to allow the loans to be repaid (principal sum and the accumulated servicing cost). This was demonstrated in 2004 when the Nigerian government applied to her foreign creditors for debt pardoning (relief), claiming the country's incapacity to continue servicing the loans while also meeting the country's immediate needs (crowding out effect). Eventually, the country got huge debt forgiveness from her two prominent creditors (namely; the Paris and London clubs). Incidentally, Nigeria's debt profile has gradually risen again with no clear economic evidence of her ability to offset the debt. There is therefore the indication of debt overhang in the circumstance of Nigeria economic climate. It is against this backdrop that this study is hinged on debt overhand/crowding out effect theory.

2.1.2 Dependency theory

Dependency theory is a theory that dealt with several issues but places more emphasis on foreign capital reliance which is associated with this study. The theory states that the advanced nations employ foreign capital as a tool to enforce a progressive arrangement that is not harmonious with the domestic requirements of the developing countries (Ijirshar, Joseph, and Godoo, 2016). The theory stresses that external borrowing serves as a modern-day slavery device whereby the Empire Countries demand more than what they have given in order to further enslave the developing countries (who were their former colonies) and rob them of the independence they claim to have gotten. These Empire Countries use inflows from debt servicing arrangement to further impoverish the developing countries, deny them of desired economic development while at the same time enlarging their empires to remain stronger, better and unbeatable. The consequence of reliance on external debt accumulation is that it becomes a mechanism through which industrialized countries exercise control over the unindustrialized nations by deciding the type of projects, level of expertise, equipment to be provided, number of expatriates and local workers, as well as all pricing decisions (Ijirshar et al., 2016). In addition, the theory contends that the dependency on external funds gives rise to too much fund outflow referred to as debt servicing which takes away the meager resources of highly indebted poor countries as well as hinder their economic growth.

2.2 Empirical Review

2.2.1 Studies outside Nigeria

Rifaqat and Usman (2012) used time series data from 1979 to 2010 to investigate the influence of external debt on Pakistan's economic development. Cointegration

analysis and Error Correction Model were used to examine the data. Their findings indicated, among other things, that external debt has a considerable negative impact on economic growth, demonstrating that a large foreign debt burden stifles growth. From 1990 to 2010, Kasidi and Said (2013) used the ordinary least squares (OLS) approach to assess the impact of external debt on Tanzania's economic development. The results indicated a strong positive link between foreign debt stock and GDP, whereas external debt servicing had a significant negative influence on GDP, according to annual time series data on external debt and economic performance obtained from the World Bank and IMF. The findings also indicated that in Tanzania, there is a long-term link between external debt and economic development.

Mukui (2013) did a study by trying to answer the questions whether external debt and debt servicing payment actually had a significant influence on the economic growth of Kenya. The study employed the linear model to analyze the impact of external debt on the economic growth of Kenya from 1980 to 2011 while including in the model some control variables such as capital formation, domestic saving, inflation, labor force, and foreign direct investment. The results indicated that external debt and debt servicing had negative impacts on economic growth. The control variables that also exerted the same negative influences include domestic saving, inflation and labor force. However, capital formation and foreign direct investment were the factors found to be having a positive and significant impact on economic growth. Thus, the study suggested policies that will increase FDI inflows in Kenya.

Siddique, Selvanathan, and Selvanathan (2015) used panel data from 40 highly indebted poor nations from 1970 to 2007 to assess the influence of foreign debt on economic growth. The ARDL cointegration technique was used to examine the data. The findings of the study indicated that these impoverished nations' foreign debt had a detrimental influence on economic growth both in the short and long run.

Akram (2016) investigated the effect of public debt on economic growth and poverty reduction in selected South Asian Countries. Panel data was collected from four South Asian countries (Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka) for a period covering 1975 to 2010 and the panel data collected was analyzed using standard panel data estimation methodologies and the results from the analysis showed that public debt had a negative impact on economic growth and poverty reduction.

Kharusi and Ada (2018) analyzed the impact of external debt on economic growth in Oman. Time series data spanning from 1990-2015 was collected from World Bank and Central bank of Oman. The data collected was analyzed using Autoregressive Distributed Lag cointegration technique and the result from the analysis indicated a negative relationship between external debt and economic growth in Oman.

Mohamed (2018) investigated the effect of external debt on the economic growth of Sudan from 1969 to 2015. Time series data collected for the study was analyzed using vector error correction method (VECM). The dependent variable for the study was GDP while external debt to exports ratio was the proxy for the external debt which was the variable of interest. Exchange rate and foreign direct investment were introduced into the model as control variables. The findings from the analysis revealed that external debt had a positive impact on Sudan's economic growth while the control variables (the exchange rate and FDI) had a negative impact on the economic growth of Sudan.

Matuka and Asafo (2018) using co-integration analysis and an error correction model, analyzed the impact of external debt on economic growth in Ghana between 1970 and 2017. Results from the time series data analyzed revealed that external have a positive impact on economic growth in Ghana both in the short run and long run.

Shkolnyk and Koilo (2018) empirically investigated the relationship between external debt and economic growth in emerging economies. Time series data spanning from 2006 to 2016 was collected and analyzed using ARDL and correlation analysis. The result from the analysis show that high level of external debt and macroeconomic instability impede economic growth in emerging economies such as Ukraine. The study recommended that the public debt management model of emerging economies should be improved.

AL-Tamimi and Jaradat (2019) examined the impact of external debt on economic growth in Jordan between 2010 and 2017 using annual time series. The data collected was analyzed using percentages, trend analysis and charts. The results from the data analyzed showed a significant negative relationship between external debt and economic growth. Thus, the study recommended an alternative source of finance other than external debt such as foreign direct investment.

2.2.2 Studies in Nigeria

Using ordinary least squares regression and secondary data, Ajayi and Oke (2012) studied the impact of foreign debt on Nigeria's economic growth and development over a 27-year period. The findings revealed that Nigeria's foreign debt burden has a negative impact on the country's national income and per capita income. The research also found that Nigeria's massive foreign debt caused depreciation of the country's currency, a weak educational system, frequent industrial strikes, a rise in worker layoffs, and unsettling economic stagnation.

Sulaiman and Azeez (2012) studied the effect of external debt on the economic growth of Nigeria using ordinary least squares (OLS) technique and other relevant

statistical tools to analyze the data obtained from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and Debt Management Office from 1970 to 2010. The study found evidence that external debt had positively contributed to Nigeria's economic growth. Although this finding is contradictory when compared with physical realities, however, the authors recommended that external debt should be acquired purely for economic growth purposes and not for political reasons.

Ekpo and Udo (2013) investigated the relationship between public debt, growth and poverty reduction in Nigeria over the period 1970-2011. The study developed a simultaneous equation model that was estimated using General Method of Moments (GMM) and the results from the analysis showed that public debt is negatively related to growth and poverty reduction in Nigeria. The study however, recommended that expenditure on social services should be promoted.

Using time series data spanning 1980 to 2010, Oyedele, Emerah, and Ogege (2013) studied the influence of external debt and debt payment on poverty reduction in Nigeria. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression was used to evaluate the data gathered. According to the findings, both foreign debt and debt payments have a negative impact on poverty reduction, implying that they both contribute to poverty in Nigeria. To effectively handle the foreign debt, the Nigerian government should generate local savings, according to this finding.

Adedoyin, Babalola, Otekinri, and Adeoti (2016) examined the short run and long run impact of external debt on economic growth in Nigeria. The study covered a period of 34 years. Annual time series data were collected from different issues of CBN statistical bulletin. The data collected was analyzed using Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) and Bound test cointegration technique and granger causality test. The findings from the study showed that there exists a long run relationship between external debt and economic growth in Nigeria. The study also revealed the existence of a significant relationship between external debt and economic growth both in the long and short run, but no causality was found among the variables. This study recommended among others that debt limit should be set and maintained to avoid debt overhang.

From 1981 through 2014, Ijirshar, Joseph, and Godoo (2016) investigated the link between external debt and economic growth in Nigeria. The time series data acquired from the CBN statistics bulletin for the study was analyzed using OLS regression analysis and an error correction model. The study's findings revealed a long-term link between foreign debt stock and economic growth, as well as the fact that external debt stock had a positive and significant influence on economic growth both in the long and short run. Furthermore, the servicing of external debt has a detrimental and severe influence on Nigeria's economic growth.

From 1981 to 2014, Monogbe (2016) examined the impact of external debt on Nigeria's economic performance. The researchers used the ordinary least squares estimation approach, co-integration test, and granger causality test to examine annual time series data. External debt and economic growth have a positive connection, according to the regression results.

Mbah, Agu, and Umunna (2016) investigated the influence of foreign debt on economic growth in Nigeria from 1970 to 2013 using an error correction model and an ARDL bound testing technique. The research discovered a long-term link between external debt and economic growth. In addition, the study found that foreign debt has a negative and considerable influence on Nigeria's economic growth.

Udeh, Ugwu, and Onwuka (2016) looked at the impact of external debt on Nigeria's economic growth. The research spanned the years 1980 to 2013. The time series data from the CBN statistics bulletin was analyzed using OLS regression technique. The regression study revealed that there is a positive link between foreign debt and Nigerian economic growth, but external debt servicing has a negative influence on growth.

In Nigeria, Afolabi, Laoye, Kolade, and Enaholo (2017) looked at the short- and long-term relationships between foreign debt and economic growth. The study's data was collected between 1980 and 2014, and it was evaluated using the granger causality test and an error correction model. The study findings indicated that Nigeria's external debt is adversely linked to economic growth. Borrowed cash, according to the research, should be used to support capital projects that promote development.

To investigate the impact of foreign debt on Nigeria's economic growth, Onakoya and Ogunade (2017) used the Autoregressive Distributed Lag and Bound test cointegration approach. The yearly time series data used in this study spanned the years 1981 to 2014. The findings of the research indicated that external debt and economic growth have a long-term link. In addition, the study discovered a negative link between external debt and Nigerian economic growth. According to the research, the Nigerian government should distribute borrowed cash to capital projects that promote growth.

Ndubuisi (2017) examined the impact of external debt on the economic growth of Nigeria using annual time series data from 1985 to 2015. The data collected was analyzed using ordinary least squares regression technique, Johansen cointegration test, and the error correction method. The variables of interest used in the study was

external debt stock and external debt servicing while exchange rate and external reserve were used as control variables. Gross domestic product was used as proxy for economic growth. The result from the regression analysis showed that debt servicing had a negative and insignificant impact on economic growth while the external debt stock had a significant positive impact on the economic growth of Nigeria. External reserve and exchange rate had significant impacts on GDP. Thus, the study recommended that external debt should be channel to infrastructural development.

Omodero and Alpheaus (2019) looked at the impact of foreign debt on Nigerian economic growth from 1997 to 2017. Data for the annual time series was gathered from the CBN statistics bulletin and the World Bank. The OLS regression approach was used to examine the data gathered. The regression result revealed that foreign debt has a substantial negative connection with economic growth, but foreign debt servicing has a strong positive link with economic growth. According to the research, the Nigerian government could resurrect abandoned businesses as a more efficient means of lowering foreign debt, generating jobs, and alleviating poverty in the country.

The impact of public debt on the Nigerian economy was examined by Eze, Nweke, and Atuma (2019). Annual time series data from the CBN statistics bulletin was collected and analyzed using the ARDL estimation approach and the Chow breakpoint test. External debt had a negative and substantial influence on GDP, whereas domestic debt had a negative but negligible effect on GDP in Nigeria, according to the study's findings. According to the research, it was recommended that the Nigerian government should stop using foreign debt to pay its budget deficit and instead rely on locally produced revenue.

2.3 Evaluation of Literature Reviewed

Most studies on public debt in Nigeria focus on the impact of public debt on economic growth rather than poverty, yet the reality remains that most of the benefits of economic growth do not reach the average Nigerian (i.e., The indigent in the society). Despite the excellent results of the beneficial influence of public debt on economic growth in several studies, there is still a need to determine if public debt has any meaningful contribution to poverty reduction in Nigeria. The influence of public debt on poverty reduction in Nigeria will be investigated in this study, which will add to the existing literature. The study is different from previous studies in scope (number of years considered is longer, 1981–2020). The two previous studies that attempted to examine the relationship between public debt and poverty reduction both ended their analysis in 2011, this study will update the scope up to 2020. A conscious effort will be made to examine the direct impact of public debt upon poverty reduction within the period of study.

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study employed ex-post facto research design. Ex-post facto design is appropriate in any after-the-fact research in which case an investigation or evaluation is carried out using already existing data (information) from the past event. Data from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) publications and the Nigerian Debt Management Office (DMO) were used for periods from 1981 through 2020 in this report. In order to determine the trustworthiness of the analytical results, the data obtained were subjected to a stationary test with Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) root test. The models constructed to capture the influence of public debt on poverty reduction were examined using the ordinary least square regression. The individual significance of the independent variables on the dependent variable was determined with reference to the values of t-statistics (probability) and all decisions were based on 5% level of significance.

3.2 Model Specification

The model specified below is similar to the model adopted by Eze, Nweke, and Atuma (2019) in their work titled public debt and economic growth in Nigeria. The functional relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables is provided in equations 3.1 below:

$$POVR = f(EXD, DD, PDS, PSENRSOCEXP)$$

$$\ln POVR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln EXD_t + \beta_2 \ln DD_t + \beta_3 \ln PDS_t + \beta_4 \ln PSENRSOCEXP_t + \mu_t$$

The Econometric form of this relationship can be stated as:

...3.2

Where POVR is poverty reduction index measure as the real per capita GDP, EXD is the external debt, DD is domestic debt, PDS is the total public debt service, PSENRSOCEXP is the primary school gross enrolment rate, SOCEXP is government expenditure on social services, and μ_t is the error term. Based on our a priori expectation,

$$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 < 0, \beta_4, \beta_5 > 0$$

3.3 Estimation Techniques

In order to develop strong, robust and reliable estimate of the parameters above, the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) estimation technique is adopted and it is upon this model that statistical and econometric test such as stationarity, co-integration, post estimation diagnostic tests, as well as the error correction mechanism will be carried out.

3.4 Data Sources

The data used for this study were obtained from secondary source. Annual data from

1981 to 2020 were obtained from different publications of the central bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin and World Development indicators (WDI) in other to achieve the objectives of the study.

4 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULT

4.1 Unit root test

Table 1: Augmented Dickey-Fuller results (1981-2020)

Variables	t-statistics	5% critical value	Remark
1 st difference			
POVR	-3.85	-3.536	Stationary
DD	-4.23	-3.536	Stationary
PDS	-3.979	-3.536	Stationary
PSENR	-5.668	-3.536	Stationary
SOCEXP	-4.780	-3.553	Stationary
2 nd difference			
EXD	-6.110	-3.544	Stationary

Source: Author's computed results (Eviews9)

The Null hypothesis states that each of the variables has unit root, that is, each is non-stationary whereas the Alternative hypothesis states that each variable does not have unit root, that is, each variable is stationary. The decision rule states that we accept the null hypothesis if the absolute value of the t-statistics is lower than the absolute critical value at 5% level of significance, otherwise we reject the null hypothesis. From Table 4.1 above, the variables POVOR, DD, PDS, PSENR and SOCEXP are stationary at 1st difference while EXD is stationary at 2nd difference.

4.2 Co-Integration Test

Since it was found that the variables under examination are integrated of order 1 and 2, a cointegration test was performed to ascertain the existence of long run relationships among the variables in the poverty reduction (POVR) model. The results of the co-integration test using the Johansen maximum likelihood procedure (Johansen and Juselius, 1990). is shown in table 4.2

Table 2: Johansen Cointegration Test Results

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.847821	181.3940	95.75366	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.659076	111.7342	69.81889	0.0000
At most 2 *	0.575820	71.91871	47.85613	0.0001
At most 3 *	0.457426	40.18760	29.79707	0.0023
At most 4 *	0.272589	17.56466	15.49471	0.0241
At most 5 *	0.144832	5.788929	3.841466	0.0161

Trace test indicates 6 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Source: Author's computed results (Eviews9)

The null hypothesis states that there is no cointegration, that is, there exist no long run relationship. And the alternative hypothesis states that there exists a long run relationship. The decision rule states that we reject the null hypothesis if at 5% level of significance the trace statistics is greater than the critical value. From our cointegration result in table 4.2, there exist 6 cointegrating equations. We conclude that there exists a long run relationship among the variables in our model. Since there exists a long run relationship, the study goes forward to estimate a short run dynamic model and a long run static model.

4.3 Short Run and Long Run Model (Error Correction Model)

Table 3: Short Run ECM Result

Variables	Coefficient	t-statistics	p-value
D(DD)	-0.168994	-1.995573	0.0566
D(DD(-1))	0.210084	1.717229	0.0978
D(EXD)	-0.103049	-2.225926	0.0349
D(EXD(-1))	0.018277	0.355472	0.7251
D(PDS)	-0.003093	-0.005768	0.9954
D(PDS(-1))	-1.318385	-3.038003	0.0054
D(PSENK)	-2.846288	-0.437489	0.6654
D(PSENK(-1))	24.71954	3.992945	0.0005

D(SOCEXP)	1.434028	3.691858	0.0010
D(SOCEXP(-1))	2.083324	4.064939	0.0004
ECM_1	-0.729481	-7.437697	0.0000
Constant	-1316.566	-3.884689	0.0006

Source: Author's computed results (Eviews9)

4: Long run Model Result

Variables	Coefficient	t-statistics	p-value
DD	0.074366	0.726836	0.4725
EXD	-0.172432	-2.992257	0.0052
PDS	-0.753086	-1.179083	0.2468
PSENR	31.23625	4.233607	0.0002
SOCEXP	2.587930	5.101888	0.0000
Constant	-2092.161	-2.973747	0.0055
R-squared	0.862956		
Adjusted R ²	0.842192		
F-statistics	41.55982		
Prob(F-statistics)	0.000000		

Source: Author's computed results (Eviews9)

4.4 Interpretation

In the short run, domestic debt (D(DD)) is negative and significant. This implies that a one percent (1%) increase in domestic debt will reduce GDP per capita by 0.169% which will invariably lead to an increase in poverty. Past period domestic debt (D(DD(-1))) is positive and insignificant. External debt (D(EXD)) is negative and statistically significant, this implies that a one percent increase in the current year external debt will reduce GDP per capita significantly, which will lead to an increase in poverty by 0.103%. the one-year period lag of External debt (D(EXD(-1))) is positive and statistically insignificant.

Further, total public debt service (D(PDS)) is negative and statistically insignificant. Past period total public debt service (D(PDS(-1))) is negative and statistically significant; this implies that a percentage increase in the previous year total public debt service will reduce GDP per capita which will invariably lead to an increase in poverty by 1.318%. The current year primary school enrollment rate (D(PSENR)) is negative and statistically insignificant. The one-year period lag of primary school enrollment rate (D(PSENR(-1))) is positive and statistically significant, this implies that a one percent increase in the previous year primary school enrollment rate will

lead to an increase in GDP per capita which will invariably lead to a significant reduction in poverty by 24.7%. Current year government expenditure on social services (D(SOCEXP)) and its previous year expenditure (D(SOCEXP(-1))) was positive and statistically significant at 5% level of significance. This implies that a one percent increase in D(SOCEXP) and D(SOCEXP(-1)) will lead to an increase in GDP per capita which will in turn lead to a reduction in poverty by 1.43% and 2.08% respectively.

The Error correction term shows how much of the disequilibrium is being corrected, that is, the extent to which any disequilibrium in the previous period is being adjusted in dependent variable at the current period. The error correction term must have a coefficient that is negative and significant. From the result, the error correction term has coefficient of -0.729 and a prob(t-value) of 0.000. This implies that the speed of adjustment is 72.9%. Constant is negative and significant, this implies that when the explanatory variables are zero, poverty reduction will be -1316.566.

From our result in table 4.4 we can see that in the long run, external debt (EXD), primary school enrollment rate (PSENR) and government expenditure on social service (SOCEXP) have significant effect on GDP per capita which was used as a proxy for poverty reduction while domestic debt (DD) and total public debt service (PDS) had an insignificant effect. From our result, external debt (EXD) which was one of the proxies for public debt had a significant negative effect on GDP per capita which was a proxy for poverty reduction in Nigeria. That is to say, a percentage increase in EXD will decrease GDP per capita which will invariably lead to an increase in poverty by 0.07% on the average. The negative effect might be as a result of mismanagement of this fund by government officials or rather as a result of the conditions attached to the debt by the country lending the loan. Furthermore, domestic debt was found to have an insignificant positive effect on poverty reduction in Nigeria. Public debt service had a negative effect on poverty reduction but this effect was not statistically significant because the t-probability value was greater than 0.05. Primary school enrollment rate (PSENR) and government expenditure on social service (SOCEXP) were found to have a positive and significant effects on poverty reduction in Nigeria.

Our overall model was significant as the F-statistic was found significant at 5% level of significance. That is to say, that our model was well specified. Also, our adjusted R^2 was 0.842, implying that 84% of the total variation in poverty reduction is explained by our independent variables. The remaining 16% is explained by the error term.

4.5 Post Diagnostic test

Reject H_0 if the p-value is less than 0.05, otherwise we fail to reject H_0 and conclude that there is no autocorrelation.

Table 5: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

F-statistic	3.754198	Prob. F(2,31)	0.347
Obs*R-squared	7.604249	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.223

Source: Author's computed results (Eviews9)

From the table above $0.223 > 0.05$, therefore we fail to reject the null hypothesis of no autocorrelation and conclude that there is no serial correlation amongst the variables.

4.6 Discussion of Findings

The findings in respect of the objectives of the study indicate that the external debt stock of Nigeria has warranted significant negative effect on the reduction of poverty both in the short run and long run; the domestic debt on the other hand exerts positive but insignificant effect on poverty reduction while total public debt servicing showed a negative but also insignificant effect on poverty reduction. The implication of this is that Nigeria might be suffering from debt overhang. When economic development of Nigeria is viewed from the point of view of poverty reduction, external debt endeavors of the Nigerian government has done more harm than good to the economy. As such, the huge resources mobilized from outside the shores of Nigeria have really increased the poverty level in the country; thus, the high foreign debt burn on Nigeria is not justified. It suggests poor management of public fund by the officials of Nigerian government and misappropriation of proceeds from external loans. On the other hand, the domestic debt stock having positive although insignificant effect on poverty reduction, indicates that loans that are mobilized locally are better utilized in economic activities that affect the living standard of the nation positively.

This findings is indicative of the fact that most of such loans mobilized in hard currencies from outside the shores of Nigeria may have ended up not being channeled into economic activities in the country but may have ended up being diverted into personal foreign accounts; this could have aided the huge amount of money reported to have been laundered into foreign countries by Nigerian public officials; otherwise, how could domestic debt show a positive effect on poverty reduction and foreign debt showed contrary result. The finding of this study agrees with Onakoya and Ogunade (2017) to the extent that external debt has significant negative impact on

economic growth but disagrees with it that domestic debt has negative impact on economic growth. The study disagrees with Abula & Ben (2016) following their finding that domestic debt stock has a direct and significant relationship with economic development and that external debt exerts insignificant impact on economic growth. The study also supports Eze, Nweke, and Atuma (2019), who found statistical evidence that external debt impacts negatively and significantly on economic development; and Okwu, et al (2016) which showed evidence of a positive effect of domestic debt stock of Nigeria on the growth of the economy measured with real GDP.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The study investigated the effect of public debts on poverty reduction in Nigeria for the period 1981-2020. A multivariate linear regression model and OLS estimation technique were utilized in the analysis. Data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin and World Development Indicators (WDI) on GDP per capita (POVR) which was used as a proxy for poverty reduction index, external debt (EXD), domestic debt (DD), total public debts service (PDS), primary school gross enrolment rate (PSEN), and government expenditure on social services (SOCEXP), were analyzed in the research. The stationarity test conducted indicated that POVR, DD, PSEN and SOCEXP were stationary after the first differencing while EXD was stationary at second difference.

The results from our analysis revealed that external debt has a negative and significant impact on poverty reduction while domestic debt has a positive but insignificant effect and public debt service a negative but insignificant effect on poverty reduction. The results also showed that primary school enrollment rate and government expenditure on social services have a positive and significant impact on poverty reduction in Nigeria. The external debt burden of this country is unjustified; the huge indebtedness of the nation associated to foreign loans has only worsen the economic performance of the nation; there has been mismanagement of the loans borrowed abroad and the huge servicing cost of such loans simply amount to erosion of the public funds. Nigerian economy has fared better with domestic debt than external debt.

5.2 Recommendations

Therefore, this study recommends that: (1) External debts should be discouraged: the national assembly should discourage the executive arm of Nigerian government from engaging in subsequent external borrowing and ensure that the institutions of government saddled with debt and finance management (the debt management office and ministry of finance) are strengthen and that laws that would checkmate misappropriation of public funds are made. (2) The Nigerian government should

resort to borrowing only when there is pressing need for that; and such loans should be sourced from within, since domestic debt has a positive relationship with poverty reduction in Nigeria, although the relationship is statistically insignificant, the government can continue to utilize domestic debt in financing fiscal deficit; but the domestic debt should be invested in social infrastructure and development.

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